

POLYSEMY AS A MEANS OF EXPRESSION AND DIFFERENT APPROACHES ON THIS ISSUE

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Annotation. This thesis discusses the phenomenon of polysemy: a single lexical form with two or more related senses (e.g. bleed to death/bleed the radiators; feed the family of five/feed the tomatoes). Since ambiguity is one of the most interesting and demanding aspects, it has been considered from several perspectives.

Key words. Phenomenon, polysemy, linguistics, phonetics, lexemes, grammatical forms, homonyms, discussion.

A polysemous word means a word that has more than one meaning. Several meanings are listed under one entry in the dictionary. For example, the word vessel has several meanings, but they all appear under one entry (as a noun) in the dictionary:

Dish ([noun](#))

- It's your turn to wash the dishes = a kind of plate.
- How long does it take to cook this dish? = a meal.

Meaning Semantics is the branch of linguistics that deals with meaning. It should be noted that there are several concepts of meaning: some of them are related to linguistic semantics, and some are not. According to Loebner, "linguistic semantics is concerned only with the meanings of linguistic expressions such as words, grammatical forms, and sentences, but not with the meanings of actions or events." Thus, a general definition of meaning is not easy. Crystal's Dictionary of Linguistics and Phonetics states that meaning is "a central concept in linguistics, used both as data and as a criterion of analysis: linguists study meaning and also use meaning as a criterion for studying other aspects of language." Meaning can be

examined from different perspectives. This includes not only linguists, but also other academic disciplines that deal with meaning, such as philosophy, psychology, sociology, neuroscience, semiotics, and statistics. The theory distinguishes many types of meaning. The author of this thesis deals with only some of them, which he considers to be the most relevant. The first dichotomy is lexical meaning and grammatical meaning. Kruse states that "if we describe the lexical meaning as the semantic information carried by the main lexical units (which we can take for now as nouns, verbs, adjectives, adverbs), then the grammatical meaning can be defined as non-sentence semantic information carried by basic lexical units". According to Lich, lexical meaning is broadly divided into seven subtypes: conceptual meaning, connotative meaning, social meaning, affective meaning, reflective meaning, compound meaning and thematic meaning. Leech conceptual meaning ('denotative' or 'cognitive' meaning also referred to as) must be the primary meaning because it is concerned with the relationship between the word and what it refers to. 7 is the main reason I give priority to the conceptual meaning puts the conceptual meaning of the seven senses as having a complex and complex organization that can be compared and correlated with similar organization on the syntactic and phonological levels of language. Took first place with its establishment. Löbner defines three levels of meaning: expressive meaning, spoken meaning, and communicative meaning. Whereas idiomatic meaning is the meaning of an expression in isolation, i.e. without context, pronunciation meaning is the meaning of an expression in a given context. Finally, the communicative meaning is the meaning of the sentence in a concrete situation. Rimer distinguishes between sentence meaning and sentence meaning.

The meaning of a sentence is "the composite meaning of a sentence made up of the meanings of individual component lexemes". So the meaning of the sentence is the meaning of the sentence. On the other hand, colloquial meaning (or also called colloquial meaning) is "the meaning used by words in a particular situation in the particular context in which they occur. A part of language, e.g. words, grammatical forms or sentences.

Lexical Ambiguity. This chapter discusses the concept of lexical meaning. Usually words have more than one meaning and sentences can also be interpreted in more than one way. This phenomenon is called ambiguity phrase or a sentence is ambiguous if it can be interpreted in more than one sense. The concept of ambiguity can be applied to all levels of meaning: expressive meaning, colloquial meaning, and communicative meaning. The theory recognizes several types of ambiguity. 8 Cruse emphasizes the importance of distinguishing between lexical ambiguity and non-lexical ambiguity because “not all ambiguity is lexical in origin.” He argues that the source of non-lexical ambiguity is mainly syntax (e.g. old men and women – only Men are old or women are old too?), but also an interpretation of simile or metaphors can lead to ambiguity. Rimer offers the following definition: From his words we can conclude that a lexeme is a linguistic unit with a lexical meaning. A lexeme can be represented by a single word, but compound expressions can also have their own lexical meaning (e.g. idioms or idioms). Loebner gives a more precise definition and says that a lexeme is defined by the following signs: (i) its sound form and spelling (for languages with a written standard) (ii) the grammatical category of the lexeme (noun, intransitive verb, and lexeme). Adjective etc.) (iii) Its specific grammatical features (for some languages, e.g gender) (iv) the set of grammatical forms it can take, particularly irregular forms (v) its lexical meaning. So, lexical semantics is related to different readings of lexemes. Lexical ambiguity is divided into two types: homonymy and polysemy (discussed below). The modern distinction between polysemy and homonymy follows the earlier distinction between complementary and opposite disambiguation established by Weinreich in 1964. Hong explains this: "Contrastive lexical ambiguity is a situation in which a lexical item is associated with at least two distinct and unrelated meanings. It should be distinguished in a full semantic description: without reference to the substance, pure formal analysis”.

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